

Energy-Efficient Edge-Domain Automation and Service Provision in 6G Networks by Deploying Offline Discovered Assignment Skills

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Abstract—Although the next generations of wireless networks are anticipated to be enabled by Artificial Intelligence (AI), the development of practical, scalable, and efficient system models and network orchestration strategies remains a significant open challenge that requires thorough investigation. In this research work, we study a system model including two parts of AI-driven management and orchestration and AI-enabled infrastructures consisting of multiple automated domains. While the network orchestration manages the autonomous domains, the intra-domain resource allocation and network slicing are also automated and AI-enabled. Consequently, we propose an efficient and scalable strategy for automating network edge domains. This approach reduces the complexity and, thus, increases the scalability and energy efficiency by implementing one Double Deep Q-Learning-based controller in each domain that can perform network slicing for multiple service types. One agent provides dynamic network services by utilizing unsupervised discovered assignment skills in an offline phase. We implement the domain controller with multiple algorithms to find the best performance and efficiency. Finally, we compare the reliability of the algorithms, and we select the algorithm that offers the best trade-off between complexity and performance.

Index Terms—6G Networks, Network Slicing, AI-Enabled, Reinforcement Learning, Energy Efficiency

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background

The extensive body of research conducted on the 6th Generation of wireless networks (6G) has introduced various innovative ideas for future networks. It is no news that Artificial Intelligence (AI) is considered a new enabler for all stages of design, control, and optimization of 6G, and thus, a wide range of AI-based solutions has been proposed in all the 6G-related scopes [1]. Nevertheless, leveraging AI within an inherently complex system presents significant challenges. The effectiveness of such a network in practice hinges on its adaptability, efficiency, scalability, and practicality. While modularity and decentralization of the network system model in 6G are evident and inevitable ([2], [3]), the same innovation appears necessary for the management and orchestration of the network. In other words, a modular and decentralized management and orchestration solution can be tailored to the decentralized network architecture and enable the required

services and innovative applications of 6G. The evolution of network management and orchestration into a distributed and automated AI-based framework not only matches the distributed and programmable 6G architecture but also guarantees high performance across the entire network [2], [3]. AI-enabled and fully automated orchestration paradigm means control loops or agents that are coordinated dynamically in the overall network in order to realize network adjustment, service provisioning, and resource allocation [3], [4]. Considering how complex, heterogeneous, and dynamic both 6G network and orchestration can become, efficiency, low complexity, scalability, and optimality come across as the new real challenge for a seamless user experience and automatic management [5]. Adaptable generic solutions can be recognized as a solution for automated and distributed AI-enabled orchestration. This work aims to illustrate a decentralized orchestration scheme and tackle edge domain network slicing by developing an automated controller.

B. Related works

This section highlights some of the recent research efforts within the broad field of 6G networks, focusing on developing overall frameworks for 6G systems using AI methodologies. Research work [4] proposes an AI-enabled architecture for 6G that consists of four layers: an intelligent sensing layer, a data mining and analytics layer, an intelligent control layer, and a smart application layer. This work suggests a Reinforcement Learning (RL)-based edge resource management since it is a model-free technique and is able to learn and take suitable actions without historical knowledge. Research work [6] proposes an RL-based decision-making framework for 6G networks that acts as the brain of the network. In this framework, the network functions have one agent for each part of the system (users, apps, edge, core, ...). Research work [7] presents an ML-based platform that enables autonomous network orchestration in 6G networks. This architecture relies on Federated Learning (FL) and provides dynamic resource management. Research work [8] proposes a two-level RL-based network orchestration and dynamic resource allocation enabled by Open Radio Access Networks (O-RAN). This

approach utilizes MARL at the first level for centralized decision-making and RL DQN for decentralized execution. Article [9] suggests a distributed orchestration and management framework for handling network slicing challenges in 6G networks. This approach benefits from hierarchical intelligent control loops for network entities. This work introduces monitoring systems and decision engines and (intra) domain management with AI assistants. Finally, authors in [2] introduce a network architecture for 6G that consists of three frameworks that operate on top of the network’s programmable infrastructures. These frameworks include the AI-driven management and orchestration framework, the fully distributed and secure AI/Machine Learning (ML) framework for crowdsourcing AI, and the BDI- and AI-driven unified and open control operations framework. All these frameworks, in addition to a closed-loop functions component, establish an adaptable 6G network architecture. The mentioned research works in this section inspired us to propose an energy-efficient generic solution for edge network domain network slicing. The next section provides the details of our motivation and how this approach goes beyond the state-of-the-art.

C. Motivation and contribution

Even though we have studied intelligent network management and orchestration, slicing, and resource allocation for 6G networks extensively [8], [10], [11], this article is the result of our attempt to have an optimal and energy-efficient yet practical network slicing solution that does not rely on any specific set of network domain specifications. Thus, in this research work, we first present the innovative features of the proposed intelligent, distributed, and automated management framework. Then, we propose a network-slicing solution and automation for edge network domains. This solution incorporates automation by deploying a controller for each domain that utilizes unsupervised discovery of assignment skills in an offline pre-training phase. In detail, in an initial offline phase, useful assignment skills are discovered that form the state space of the controller. Therefore, one simple and efficient controller can support multiple service types. In other words, instead of utilizing complex, intelligent controllers, we simplify and generalize the complex environment and network slicing procedure for the controller since the main goal of this work is to propose a solution that is decentralized, generalized, scalable, energy-efficient, and optimal. The objective of tackling a complex task within a sophisticated system efficiently drives this work to surpass current state-of-the-art solutions. The next section presents the considered system model and the proposed solution in detail.

II. THE PROPOSED GENERIC SOLUTION

A. The modular system model and pre-training phase

Building on insights from [2], [3], our proposed framework is based on the fact that the 6G network architecture and orchestration framework are inherently modular and decentralized. As illustrated in Fig. 1, our network design incorporates an AI-driven management and orchestration framework (Fig.

Fig. 1. Network system model: (a) the AI-based network orchestration and automated infrastructures, (b) hierarchical levels of management

Fig. 2. Edge domain management

1(a)), in which modules carry out management tasks across multiple levels (Fig. 1(b)) by implementing a fully distributed, dynamic architecture with computing nodes deployed across the far-edge, edge, and cloud domains. These distributed nodes host virtualized functions of the software-defined disaggregated RAN and core network, virtual applications, and AI agents, all dynamically orchestrated to support holistic network control and management strategies. Beyond centralized orchestration that coordinates domains collectively, each domain also features internal automation to optimize local operations.

Inspired by [12], we consider that each network edge domain consists of various resource pools, of an offline pre-training phase that discovers useful assignment skills for simplifying the environment and service provision, and of an intelligent domain controller, as presented in Fig. 2.

In the pre-training phase, an unsupervised RL agent generates distinct arrays that each include elements displaying a percentage of one resource type. We follow the idea of having four types of resources in every edge domain, including bandwidth resources, computational resources, memory, and energy resources. Therefore, each array or assignment skill consists of four elements. These skills shape the state space of the intelligent controller. Thus, when a skill is selected by the controller, the elements of the array show the percentage of each resource type that will be allocated. All the percentages are bound to the lower limit of 2 and upper limit of 20 percent [12]. The result of the pre-training phase is a set of 64 useful skills that were discovered without a hand-craft reward or dependencies on the quantity of the resource pools [12]. Since the pre-training phase occurs in an offline mood, it is

TABLE I
SERVICE TYPES

Service types	Peak data rate (Gbps)	Experienced data rate (Gbps)	Maximum bandwidth (GHz)	Computation latency (ms)	Reliability	Energy efficiency
eeMBB	> 1000	< 1	< 100	< 1	0.9	Nominal
emMTC	Not critical	Not critical	Not critical	Not critical	0.9	Nominal
emMTC+URLLC	Not critical	> 1	Not critical	< 10	0.9	Nominal

not affected by the domain controller either. As a result, one generic set of assignment skills that was discovered for all the network edge domains (i.e., not dependent on domains' details) simplifies the state and action space of the domain controller.

After simplifying the environment and service provision procedure, we proceed to the development of the controller. Our goal is to develop a controller that presents the best trade-off between efficiency and robustness. At the level of the domain controller, we consider these three service types for the network tenants : extreme enhanced Mobile Broadband (eeMBB), extreme massive Machine-Type Communications (emMTC), and extreme massive Machine-Type Communications + Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications (emMTC + URLLC). Table I presents how each service type is defined.

As shown in Table I, data rate and reliability are deterministic Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for eeMBB service. On the other hand, emMTC+URLLC service is time-sensitive, and reliability is very essential for this type of service. In addition, services that include machine-type communications are engaged with low-power and/or basic devices. Therefore, these service types are not compatible with high-power or high-computational communication techniques. Hence, providing each service requires designing a different reward system and requires a different agent and training phase. However, since we incorporated the offline pre-training phase, a single RL agent will be able to provide various services in edge domains.

B. The network domain controller

The main contribution of this work is the development of an efficient controller for intra-domain network slicing and service provision by utilizing the output of the offline phase. As a well-known ML-based promising technique for online decision-making, we focus on RL techniques. The RL agent is required to provide a slice of the domain resources for any of the service types eeMBB, emMTC, and emMTC + URLLC using the discovered skills at the pre-training level. The rationale behind including a pre-assignment level is that choosing the proper quantity from each resource pool in order to provide the required QoS for each service type can be challenging for the controller. Each resource pool can be considered as an interval of possible quantities to choose from. The interval includes infinite real numbers, and only a finite set of numbers is useful. This means that the RL agent will receive rewards in sparse states. Receiving rewards plays an important role the process of learning for RL agents. Thus, a state space with sparse reward states is challenging for the agent. Having multiple service types with different goals makes this

challenge more difficult for the agent to tackle. However, by discovering useful assignment skills [12], the action space is discretized for the agent, and thus, the controller will select a sequence of useful skills to develop the network slice. By reducing the action space of the domain controller to a discrete action space, the state space, action space, and tasks of the agent will be as follows:

State space= { percentage of bandwidth pool, percentage of memory pool, percentage of power , percentage of computational resource pool }

Action space = { skill 1, skill 2, skill 3, ... , skill 64 }

Tasks = { eeMBB, emMTC, emMTC + URLLC }

After discretizing and simplifying the action space, a single RL agent can perform the tasks by defining a proper reward system.

The specifications of the problem and environment suggest the use of an algorithm that can perform with continuous state space and discrete action space. While Deep Q-Networks (DQN) [13], as a baseline algorithm, seems efficient and sufficient, we try to compare the performance of DQN with Double DQN (DDQN) [14] and Dueling DQN [15] to find the best performance. This is because, in DQN, the same value is used by the *max* operation to select and evaluate an action, which can result in selecting overestimated values and, thus, over-optimistic value estimates. Consequently, even though DQN is relatively efficient, it suffers from overestimation of Q-values, which can affect performance. DDQN tries to reduce over-estimations by benefiting from another network called the target network for evaluation. Therefore, even though the action selection and the action's Q-value evaluation are not fully decoupled, the *max* operation is decomposed into action selection and action evaluation. On the other hand, in Dueling DQN, the network is split into two streams to calculate the state-value function and advantage function. Hence, the network produces separate estimates of both automatically and without supervision [14], [15]. As a result, we implement the controller with DDQN and Dueling DQN in addition to DQN to compare the performance. In the next section, the details of the implementation are provided. Moreover, we compare the performance of all three controllers in the next section and select the most efficient one, considering performance and computational complexity.

III. IMPLEMENTATION AND TECHNICALITIES

A. Implementation and simulation results

This work was implemented with Python 3.10.12 and Pytorch 2.4.0. The environment was coded using the Gym library. The hardware-based computational resource information is available in Table II. The simulations include an environment

$$\text{State space} = \{[0 - 5]\%, [0 - 5]\%, [0 - 5]\%, [0 - 5]\%\} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Action space} = \text{skill set} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \{bandwidth(\%), \text{ memory}(\%), \text{ computational resources}(\%), \text{ power}(\%)\} \\ \{bandwidth(\%), \text{ memory}(\%), \text{ computational resources}(\%), \text{ power}(\%)\} \\ \dots \\ \{bandwidth(\%), \text{ memory}(\%), \text{ computational resources}(\%), \text{ power}(\%)\} \end{array} \right\} \quad (3)$$

with a continuous state space and discrete action space as the network edge domain in addition to three algorithms: DQN, DDQN, and Dueling DQN as the controller. The environment was implemented as follows: The state space includes four continuous values, each presenting the percentage of bandwidth, memory, computational resources (e.g., processors), and power. The action space consists of 64 arrays with four elements. The action space is the set of unsupervised discovered assignment skills obtained in the offline pre-training phase. This phase was implemented according to [12]. Therefore, the state and action space are presented in (2) and (3).

The environment receives a task number showing which one of the tasks, eeMBB, emMTC, or emMTC + URLLC is needed. The task selection process is random for every episode of the training. An episode starts with a given task and ends in two cases; either the task is provided or the maximum time steps, which is set to 100 steps, have been reached. The first ending criteria is tightly related to the reward system as presented in Algorithm 1. With Table I in mind, we analyze the relationship between the types of the resource pools and the task to design the reward system. Even though bandwidth directly affects the data rate, assigning enough computational resources and memory is also essential. More over, computational resources and memory play an important role when providing time-sensitive services since they are directly involved in computational latency. On the other hand, while power is essential for consistent and error-free communications, service types emMTC and emMTC + URLLC need to operate with low power because of the nature of their users.

Accordingly, for the eeMBB, we consider the main objective of the service type to is to achieve a high data rate. Providing a high data rate requires a high percentage of all the resources. In addition, this service is not limited to power allocation (e.g., emMTC) and/or delay sensitivity (e.g., emMTC + URLLC). Thus, the main portion of the reward is based on the provided data rate. When the provided data rate meets the requirements, the final state is met, and while receiving the reward the episode ends (lines 4-6). However, as we desire a power percentage upper than the power mid-range among all the skills, a smaller portion of the total reward is assigned to the agent for that (lines 2-3). Equation 1 shows the calculation of the data rate in which SNR represents the Signal to Noise Ratio. As we are managing the edge domains, we consider the communication to be through millimeter-wave (mmWave) frequency with an SNR rate of $[0, 20]$ dB.

$$R = 2 * Bandwidth * \log_2(1 + SNR) \quad (1)$$

While in emMTC a high data rate is not needed, the users are

not capable of having high-power communications. Hence, if the action chooses the skills that assign the lowest percentages of power (with a 5 percent tolerance from the least percentage of power that exists among the skills), the agent receives the bigger portion of the reward, and the goal of the agent is met (lines 12-14). So when this criteria is met, the episode ends. However, in order to have an efficient assignment, smaller portions of the reward will be assigned to the agent if the assigned skills provide low percentages of bandwidth (lines 8-9) and computational resources (lines 10-11). This is compared to the mid-range of these two resource types in the set of skills.

Algorithm 1 Reward system and episode ending criteria

```

1 TASK eeMBB :
2   if power > mid - range power in {Skills} :
3     reward += (20 % of total reward)
4   if data rate > 1000 Gbps :
5     reward += (80 % of total reward)
6     episode end = true
7 TASK emMTC :
8   if bandwidth < mid-range bandwidth in {Skills}:
9     reward += (20 % of total reward)
10  if computational resources > mid-
    range computational resources in {Skills} :
11    reward += (20 % of total reward)
12  if power ∈ [min power in {Skills} % , min power
    in {Skills} + 5%] :
13    reward += (60 % of total reward)
14    episode end = true
15 TASK emMTC + URLLC :
16  if memory > mid - range memory in {Skills} :
17    reward += (15 % of total reward)
18  if computational resources < mid-
    range computational resources in {Skills} :
19    reward += (15 % of total reward)
20  if bandwidth < one-third bandwidth in {Skills}:
21    reward += (15 % of total reward)
22  if power ∈ [min power in {Skills} % , min power
    in {Skills} + 5%] :
23    reward += (55 % of total reward)
24    episode end = true

```

Last but not least, the reward system for service type emMTC + URLLC targets to encourage providing rapid communication while the transmission power stays low and the assignment is efficient. Thus, the reward is divided into four portions to help the agent choose skills with a low percentage of power (lines 22-23) yet high percentages of computational resources (lined 18-19) and memory (lines 16-17) since this

TABLE II
IMPLEMENTATION AND TRAINING PARAMETERS

(Hyper)parameter	Value
Learning rate	0.0001
γ	0.99
ϵ	0.01
Expeloration rate	Linear
Optimizer	RMSprop
CPU model	Intel(R) Xeon(R)
CPU cores	1
Clock speed	2.20 GHz
Cache size	56320 KB

Fig. 3. Training reward and loss for 100,000 episodes

service is time-sensitive. The last portion of the reward is for the bandwidth (lines 20-21) to stay higher than the one-third range.

It is relevant to mention that the total reward of each episode is normalized to be between 0 and 1 at the end of each episode. This is attributed to a more stable training process and precise results.

In the training phase, each algorithm was trained for 100,000 episodes with the hyperparameters presented in Table II. This set of selections were inspired by the original papers introducing DQN, DDQN, and Dueling DQN [13]–[15] and later were adjusted after multiple training trials. While γ and ϵ show the discount factor and exploration rate, respectively, the exploration rate decay happens linearly. The deployed optimizer is Root Mean Square Propagation (RMSprop) which is suitable for our non-stationary problem. Fig. 3 presents the reward and loss mean of the training phase for all algorithms. The reward plot shows a slow increase in the mean of every last 100 normalized episode rewards, starting from 3.2 to 3.5. The loss converges to zero after 60,000 episodes and stays stable. While all the training results show a stable training phase, we will compare the results of each algorithm in the next section more closely. We continue this section by presenting the test results.

For each task, every agent was tested for 100 episodes in order to see the reliability of the controller for emMTC+URLLC

Fig. 4. Reliability

Fig. 5. Computational latency (slice allocation time)

service since it imposes the most challenging task for the agent. The reliability was calculated as the ratio of successfully assigned slices that met the predefined QoS requirements to the total number of slice assignments. As Fig. 4 demonstrates, DQN and DDQN agents show more reliability, while Dueling DQN shows a poor performance in this problem setting.

Finally, Fig. 5 presents the computational delay when each agent was tested to perform network slicing tasks. This delay was calculated by observing the run time of a test for 1000 episodes. DDQN performs emMTC+ URLLC with the least computational time. It shows the same performance as Dueling DQN for emMTC and as DQN for eeMBB. The next section studies the comparison for the complexity, delay, and performance of all agents.

B. Analyzing the Results, Complexity, and Efficiency

This section provides the final results of this work by comparing the experiments in order to select the most proper controller for automating the edge domains. We compare the algorithms in terms of performance, complexity, and required computations.

1) *Complexity and required computations:* DQN can be considered the agent with the most efficiency in the structure. While DDQN needs two neural networks to evaluate the Q-value of the action, DQN uses only one network. The second network in DDQN adds some additional computation and time while training. Dueling DQN uses only one neural network but with a different structure that splits into two streams. This architecture introduces slightly more complexity. The training time for DQN, DDQN, and Dueling DQN were 26.2, 26.3, and 30.66 minutes, respectively. In the test phase, DDQN outperformed other controllers with a difference of 1 ms with Dueling DQN and 0.5 ms with DQN. For emMTC, Dueling DQN and DDQN outperformed DQN with a difference of 1 ms. While we do not consider the differences between the agents in terms of training time and implementation

TABLE III
PERFORMANCE AND COMPLEXITY COMPARISON

Controller	Implementation complexity	Training time	Computational latency	Reliability (emMTC+URLLC)
DQN	<i>Baseline</i>	26.2	3 << 5.5 ms	94%
DDQN	> <i>Baseline</i>	0.38% + <i>Baseline</i>	3 << 4.5 ms	98%
Dueling DQN	> <i>Baseline</i>	16.87% + <i>Baseline</i>	4 << 5.5 ms	80%

complexity to be determinative, the computational time for service emMTC+URLLC suggests that DDQN can be selected as the best controller.

2) *Performance*: According to Algorithm 1, a successful service provision requires pursuing a different goal for each task. The reward system and ending criteria was designed to encourage the controllers to provide a high data rate for eeMBB by assigning more bandwidth and power, to provide an agile communication with low power and bandwidth for emMTC, and to provide a low-latency and low-power service for emMTC+URLLC. The successful service provision episodes were monitored to compare how reliable every agent is. Standard DQN showed a promising performance by success rates more than 90 % for all services. However, DDQN showed the most reliable performance for emMTC+URLLC and promising performance for the rest of services. Dueling DQN performance was not acceptable for services emMTC and emMTC+URLLC. Table III summarises the comparison conducted in this section and suggests that DDQN can be the best controller in our designed system.

3) *Energy Efficiency*: Energy efficiency at the management level is directly linked to the complexity of the management approach. Our proposed network edge domain approach improves energy efficiency by developing a network edge domain automation that benefits from following factors:

- One offline pre-training phase simplifies the domain for the agent to interact with and reduces its action space considerably.
- The pre-training phase includes one training, and the output is applicable to all the network edge domains [12].
- One single RL agent automates network slicing and provides multiple service types in the edge domains.
- Since the domains are intrinsically similar, and the output of the offline phase does not depend on the details of the domains, the same trained controller can be implemented in all the domains.

The aforementioned points demonstrate how our proposed scheme minimizes computational requirements, leading to significant improvements in energy efficiency.

IV. CONCLUSION

Seeing that future wireless networks introduce different levels of performance and characteristics, practical AI-enabled system models and orchestration strategies are yet to be addressed when developing the next generation. Hence, this work was an attempt to review an AI-enabled modular and scalable system model with multi-domain infrastructures. In addition to the network's overall management and orchestration part, each domain was considered to be automated.

Then, we proposed a controller for intra-domain network slicing proper for network edge domains with resource pools. This controller benefits from previously learned skills and, thus, can perform multiple slicing tasks while being efficient and scalable. The controller was implemented with different algorithms in the edge domains. After a thorough comparison, the DDQN agent was selected as the most proper controller regarding performance and efficiency.

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